

Keynote Address

Aligning the summative and formative purposes of assessment: Assignment design, feedback and moderation at scale

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Abstract

This paper discusses the complexities of assessment practices in large university classes, emphasising the balance between summative and formative purposes to improve teaching and learning. Large classes, often defined as having over 100 students, pose challenges for lecturers such as increased workload, reduced interaction, and difficulty providing consistent feedback. The study focuses on a first-year psychology course with over 1500 students, implementing strategies like exemplars with detailed rubrics, audio feedback, and rigorous moderation. These methods aim to enhance understanding of assessment standards and foster continuous improvement. Reflections by the author suggest that integrating formative elements into summative assessments can significantly enhance learning outcomes and student engagement, even in large class settings.

Keywords: *Summative assessment; Formative assessment; Feedback; Moderation; Large class; Higher education*

1. Introduction

Designing an assessment effectively is a complex process, particularly as there are inbuilt tensions between its certification and enhancement of learning purposes; the fundamental double duty of assessment (Carless, 2015), with implications for task and rubric design, alignment with teaching approaches and learning outcomes, provision of feedback, monitoring of progress, evaluation of quality work and student role. This complexity is magnified when teaching large class cohorts. There is no agreed definition for the term ‘large class’; however, there seems to be general agreement that student numbers of >100 can be considered to fit this definition (Exeter *et al.*, 2010). Teaching a large class presents significant challenges in designing, managing, and standardising assessment practices (Broadbent *et al.*, 2017).

This paper reports on the alignment of the formative and summative purposes of assessment in the context of a very large class cohort (1500+) with specific reference to assignment design, provision of feedback and moderation across a large set of tutors. This paper supports the keynote presentation for the PHELC24 online symposium.

2. Large Classes in Higher Education

There is no agreed definition of the term ‘large class’ in the higher education context (Maringe & Sing, 2014). This was particularly evident in one study in which 66 academics quantified unmanageable class sizes as numbering between 30 to 1,500 students (Mantai & Huber, 2021). Most studies seem to have settled on 100 or more students to the term ‘large class’ (Exeter *et al.*, 2010). However, regardless of the quantification of class size, the challenges associated with teaching at scale are likely linked as much to teacher perception as student numbers (Maringe & Sing, 2014). Higher education teachers may associate class size with increased workload and hindering meaningful instruction (Allais, 2014). They may also be perceived as hindering achievement, performance (Hornsby & Osman, 2014) and learning because less discussion and interaction is leading to passivity (Mulryan-Kyne, 2010).

3. Assessment at Scale in Higher Education

Assessment is one pillar of a wider pedagogical ecosystem, which also includes teaching, learning and curriculum, all of which are bound by relationships and values (Nind *et al.*, 2016). Within that ecosystem, assessment is sometimes viewed as the most important element, which, if badly conceived, designed and implemented, may render teaching and learning ineffective (Biggs & Tang, 2011). Moreover, while students might evade the teaching practices of a programme, they are “unequivocally compelled to participate in the assessment process” (Sambell *et al.*, 2017, p.140), which profoundly impacts what students and teachers do (Carless, 2015) and likely what they choose not to do.

Assessment in higher education has been influenced by a relatively limited range of perspectives (Boud *et al.*, 2018), with research in the field generally focusing on one aspect of the assessment process while simultaneously, by default, rendering other aspects invisible (Ajjawi *et al.*, 2021).

As well as the challenges posed for teaching and learning as outlined above, large class cohorts can present real challenges in terms of assessment design, management and standardisation of practices, the implications of which have not been well researched (Broadbent *et al.*, 2017). Due to the sheer scale of a large class, it may be perceived that assessment options are limited (Kerr, 2011); that continuous assessment is not feasible (De Matos-Ala & Hornsby, 2015); and that meaningful feedback is difficult to provide (Allais, 2014; Broadbent *et al.*, 2017). Having said that, technology has allowed higher education teachers to assess learning in-class (Voelkel & Bennett, 2014), providing feedback for both teachers and students instantly at a whole class level.

4. An Example of Summative Assessment with a Formative Flavour: Design, Feedback and Moderation at Scale

This case study focuses on a first-year psychology subject comprising 1500 students distributed across four campuses, including a fully online context. The subject examines behavioural changes related to health and wellbeing and is taught over eleven weeks in one semester. Students are tasked with undertaking changes in their health behaviours and reflecting on these changes through various forms of assessment, including ten weekly online quizzes, three linked reflective journal entries, and an end-of-term examination. The reflective journal is the central assignment, designed to integrate both summative and formative assessment elements. Over the years, curriculum, teaching and assessment practices have been formally evaluated many times, resulting in iterative changes.

4.1. Assignment Design

The journal assignment is developed within the authentic assessment paradigm, requiring students to engage in real-world tasks by applying behavioural change theory to their contexts. The assignment accounts for 60% of the overall subject mark and consists of three iterative phases. In each phase, students create a two-minute video and complete a 700-900 word written component. Each subsequent phase builds on the previous one, with increasing complexity and decreasing support. (see Figure 1 for more detail). This design aims to balance the dual purposes of assessment—certification of learning and enhancement of learning.

To address students' reluctance to engage with non-graded tasks (Jessop *et al.*, 2014), each of the three journal entries attracts a grade. This approach ensures that students remain

motivated to complete the assignments while receiving ongoing formative feedback that enhances their learning and performance.

Figure 1. Three linked health behaviour journal assessments. (Figure taken from Broadbent et al., 2017)

4.2. Use of Exemplars and Rubrics

Formative feedback is built into the assessment process to improve learning (Shute, 2008) at whole class and individual levels. Students often struggle to evaluate quality through rubrics alone (Dawson, 2017). To mitigate this, exemplars are provided alongside detailed rubrics to illustrate the expectations for each task explicitly. The exemplar mirrors each of the three journal phases, offering students a concrete example of high-quality work. This strategy ensures consistent messaging and helps students understand the standards required for success. The exemplars and rubrics together foster a clearer understanding of assessment criteria, encouraging students to self-assess and improve their work based on these benchmarks. This approach ensures that the same message reaches each student in the same manner at a whole class level.

4.3. Provision of Feedback

Providing meaningful feedback in large classes is challenging, but audio feedback offers a practical solution. Audio feedback can convey more nuance and detail than written comments and is often perceived as more personal and engaging by students. In this case study, markers provide personalised audio feedback for each journal entry, focusing on current performance and offering specific guidance for future improvement. This feedback method not only saves time for educators but also enhances the quality of feedback, thereby supporting student learning more effectively.

The iterative nature of the assessment tasks, where feedback from one task informs the next, promotes continuous improvement and deeper learning. This approach aligns well with formative assessment principles, emphasising the importance of using assessment to support learning rather than to measure it. Feedback is designed to be actionable, helping students understand what they did well and how they can improve in future assignments (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. How the assessment, exemplar and feedback in the case study fit together.

(Figure taken from Broadbent et al., 2017)

4.4. Moderation Across Tutors

Ensuring consistency and equity in feedback is crucial, especially with a large number of tutors involved. Rigorous moderation processes are enacted before and during the marking

and feedback phases. Detailed resources and training are provided for tutors to ensure they understand the assessment criteria and can deliver consistent, high-quality feedback. A subsample of assignments is double-marked by different tutors to check for consistency in grading standards. Additionally, three full-time subject staff moderate across the team, providing personalised audio feedback to part-time tutors. This feedback includes examples of how to improve the quality of their grading and formative feedback.

Tutors are encouraged to observe their peers' feedback methods to evaluate and enhance their own practices. This peer observation and feedback loop helps to ensure that all students receive fair and consistent feedback, which is critical in maintaining the integrity of the assessment process in large classes.

Figure 3. the marking and audio moderation process.

(Figure taken from Broadbent et al., 2017; also see Broadbent, 2018)

5. Advice for Implementing Formative Practices in Large Classes

The implementation of summative assessments with formative elements in large classes offers significant insights for educators aiming to enhance student learning while managing practical constraints. This approach, as demonstrated in the description above, integrates exemplars, rubrics, and audio feedback to create a more effective and engaging learning environment.

For educators considering the integration of formative elements into summative assessments in large classes, several practical strategies can be gleaned from this study.

Here are key recommendations:

1. **Utilise exemplars with rubrics:** Using exemplars accompanied by detailed rubrics and feedback allowed students to understand the standards expected in their assessments. By providing concrete examples of high-quality work, students were better able to grasp the criteria for success and were more likely to engage deeply with the material. This method fosters a clearer understanding of assessment standards and encourages students to self-assess and improve their work based on these benchmarks. It is recommended that exemplars should be made available online to ensure all students have equal access. Annotations or video explanations of how the rubric applies to the exemplar can further clarify expectations.
2. **Implement audio feedback:** Audio feedback helped us address the challenges of providing detailed, personalised feedback in large classes. We found that audio feedback could convey more nuance and detail than written comments and was often perceived as more personal and engaging by students. We found this method saved time and enhanced the quality of feedback, thereby supporting students' learning more effectively. However, it is essential to provide training and support for markers unfamiliar with this technology to overcome any technical barriers.
3. **Iterative assessments:** The iterative nature of the assessment tasks, where feedback from one task informed the next, promoted continuous improvement and deeper learning. This approach aligns well with the principles of formative assessment, which emphasise the importance of using assessment to support learning rather than to measure it. We recommend that assessment tasks are designed so that feedback from one task informs the next. Breaking down larger assessments into linked summative tasks can also help manage workload while providing opportunities for students to apply feedback.
4. **Rigorous moderation:** Rigorous moderation processes ensured that all students received equitable feedback, which is crucial in large class settings where variability in marking can be a significant issue. This includes providing formative audio feedback to markers and regular calibration sessions to align grading standards.

6. Conclusion

The integration of formative elements into summative assessments, particularly in large class settings, offers a balanced approach that addresses both the need for clear, consistent standards and the enhancement of student learning. The study demonstrates that exemplars, detailed rubrics, and audio feedback can significantly improve the quality and impact of assessments. By using these tools, educators can provide more personalised and actionable feedback, fostering a learning environment where students can continuously improve and

engage deeply with the material. For more details about these practices see Broadbent (2018) and Broadbent *et al.*, (2017).

Acknowledgements: Thanks to Ann-Marie Farrell for her help putting this paper together.

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